

Publisher: Scientific-Professional Society for Disaster Risk Management

International Journal of Disaster Risk Management

Journal homepage: <https://internationaljournalofdisasterriskmanagement.com>

Research Article

Implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management

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Received: 1 October 2024; Revised: 5 December 2024; Accepted 15 October; Published: 25 December

ABSTRACT

The high mortality rates resulting from the disaster have led to significant losses. This study is of utmost importance as it aims to evaluate the implementation of the four thematic areas of disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM) in the Secondary Public Schools located in the Province of Benguet Philippines. The study also aims to identify the variations in implementing DRRM across the participating schools and the challenges and training needs related to DRRM. While the findings indicate a high level of implementation for disaster prevention and mitigation, preparedness, recovery, and rehabilitation, disaster response needs improvement in the implementation. DRRM raises various concerns among institutions, such as lack of budget, multiple tasks assigned to the school DRRM coordinator, and insufficient parental support. However, with the right interventions, these challenges can be overcome. Moreover, public school educators must receive training in the field of DRRM, such as basic life support training, first aid training, contingency training, and incident command systems, which presents an opportunity for improvement. As a result, a lack of resources, emergency supplies, communication systems, and effective response mechanisms will not be delivered, and this can turn out to be disastrous to the learners and the teachers. With this, collaboration needs to be established with other government agencies and the private sector.

KEYWORDS

DRRM, Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management, Implementation of DRRM, four thematic Areas of DRRM, Challenges in the Implementation of DRRM

1. Introduction

Dealing with resiliency towards disaster is a major concern involving education. With a huge fall-back when a community is devastated by natural or human-induced hazards, class disruption and the quality of education will not be delivered. Numerous reasons aggravate the worsening of a disaster, leading to a greater impact that affects society. Save the Children (2016) asserts that disasters influence children, adolescents, and educational institutions annually. The right to a high-quality education is a fundamental entitlement for every child. However, the impact of calamities has resulted in many children in the region being unable to exercise this right. The exacerbation of educational inequities can occur due to various reasons, such as inadequate site selection, architecture, or

development resulting in damage or destruction of schools, the utilization of schools as evacuation centres, and insufficient backing of disaster risk reduction (DRR) policies by the authorities and the public at large. Additionally, if education is encouraged before, during, and following calamities, lives can be saved, children can be protected, and entire communities and nations can benefit. Schools can thereby increase the effectiveness of humanitarian efforts, lessen vulnerabilities, and enhance risk mitigation for potential risks.

Consequently, the incorporation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management into the educational curriculum has been mandated to ensure the safety of students and equip them with knowledge of disaster management. This measure has been implemented in basic education institutions. DepEd Order 83, S. 2011, and DepEd Order 21, S. 2015 pertain to implementing disaster preparedness measures, disaster risk reduction, management coordination, and information management protocols in schools.

All agencies should discuss and execute disaster Risk Reduction and Management from the highest levels of government to the grassroots level and from preschool to the tertiary level. The students need to comprehend Disaster Risk Reduction and Management from its basics to its complexity. However, more is required to let them understand its concept; it is important to show them its application in the daily operation of an institution so that they can better incorporate the theory and application. Meanwhile, it has been observed during past calamities that when classes are suspended due to tropical cyclones or any adverse potential hazards, many of the students do not heed the warnings seriously; instead, they tend to take their time roaming around for various reasons, whether for pleasure, livelihood, or to take videos for social media, which puts their lives at risk. In addition, during multiple trainings conducted, it was noticeable that many students needed more knowledge of DRRM, particularly its policies. Some have minimal knowledge, while others are unaware of the consequences. Also, only a few know what to do before, during, and after disasters. Moreover, some students claim that they have yet to encounter DRRM as a subject or a topic during their junior and senior high school years, which makes them prone to different hazards.

1.1 Review of Literature

The comprehensive execution of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) across various national agencies and local government units is not just a complex undertaking but a crucial one. In different training sessions and during deployment in the different parts of the Cordillera, it is observed that many stakeholders need more knowledge of DRRM, particularly its policies and other legal bases. Some have minimal knowledge, while others are unaware of this system, highlighting the urgent need for its understanding and implementation.

The Philippines is vulnerable to multiple hazards due to its geographic location. According to Bollettino et al. (2018), the Philippines is prone to natural calamities such as earthquakes, volcanoes, floods, landslides, drought, and the transmission of illnesses like malaria and dengue. This vulnerability is due to its geographical location, where there are two major tectonic plates and it is also located in the Pacific where typhoons frequently develop. The area where these typhoons form is known as the 'typhoon belt'. In addition, the country is surrounded by active volcanoes, a region known as the 'Ring of Fire', and is situated in the Pacific typhoon belt, rendering 60% of its total land area susceptible to natural hazards. In addition, Mina (2021) also mentions that the World Risk Index states that 74% of the country's population is affected by these calamities.

In retrospect of the history of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) in the Philippines, the National Disaster Coordination Council (NDCC) was established based on Presidential Decree 1566, which is also referred to as Strengthening the Philippine Disaster Control, Capability, and Establishment of the National Program on Community Disaster Preparedness. After 36 years, PD 1566 was enacted, and the country encountered numerous devastating calamities. It may be a natural hazard, a human-induced hazard, or a combination. It has been observed that during this time, disaster management concentrated on disaster relief and response, which needed to be more dressed and delivered better disaster management.

Meanwhile, the cascading of the DRRM program from the national government to the grassroots community is somewhat straggling. According to Agub (2017), Line agencies and LGUs need more resources to implement the mandates that the DRRM law requires the office to perform. Another commonly cited issue in disaster management is the need for national and local governments to carry out their duties concerning DRRM effectively. Several factors contribute to the issue, including a shortage of personnel, insufficient technical proficiency, insufficient financial funding, and technological capabilities such as multiple-hazard early warning devices.

With that, The Department of Education (DepEd) has taken a proactive step by releasing a set of regulations dubbed the Basic Education Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DO 37, s. 2015). It is a significant move to strengthen the implementation of DRRM in the educational sectors and set a pattern to expand its efforts in schools and offices. In addition, this will also guarantee that education will continue, even during and after catastrophic events or emergencies, and that the level of quality will not be affected. Furthermore, the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management School Manual Book 1 from the Department of Education was used in this study. This comprehensive manual, formulated by the Department of Education, serves as a template for the localization, conceptualization, and adaptation of DRRM to the sub-national context. The components of this manual include the background and rationale, the basic framework of DRRM in basic education, and the three (3) Pillars of the Comprehensive Approach to Basic Education. It helps explore the scope of DRRM implementation and integration in schools, covering all three (3) pillars as a guide to its application. Safe Learning Environments, School Disaster and Risk Reduction, and Building Educational Resilience. The Department of Education (DepEd) issued a guideline entitled "Comprehensive Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) in the Basic Education Framework" to steer the disaster risk reduction and management efforts in the basic education sector towards resilience-building in schools and offices.

2. Methods

This study utilized descriptive quantitative research to determine the Implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in Basic Education in the Province of Benguet. Descriptive research is a study that systematically describes the participants accurately. A survey-based design was used to produce the needed data.

The study was conducted at the Province of Benguet's secondary public schools, main and extension. The participants were from eighteen (18) different schools. The questionnaire, a key tool in this study, was meticulously developed by the research team and underwent a rigorous evaluation process to ensure its quality. Using Cronbach's Alpha to measure its internal consistency, the evaluation yielded a result of 0.926, interpreted as excellent.

The researcher rigorously adhered to ethical protocols while administering the questionnaire, ensuring the study's integrity. These protocols included obtaining informed consent from the participants, ensuring their anonymity and confidentiality, and respecting their right to withdraw from the study at any time. The researcher sought authorization from the superintendent of the Benguet school division to carry out the study and administer the questionnaire to the secondary public schools. Next, the researcher sought permission from the school principal to distribute the survey questionnaires to the designated school coordinators for DRRM. The study's analytical approach was robust, using descriptive statistics. Frequency count and to answer the extent of the implementation of DRRM, the four thematic weighted means were used as the statistical tool. The Kruskal-Wallis Test, a non-parametric test used to compare more than two independent groups when the dependent variable is ordinal, was utilized to determine if there was a significant difference in the implementation of DRRM regarding the municipal classification where the school is located.

3. Results

3.1 The extent of implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management

Disaster Risk Reduction and Management reduces natural and man-made disaster risks. It includes identifying risks, preparing, responding, recovering, and reducing them. DRRM implementation varies widely by country and region. It is due to governance, economic capacity, public awareness, and local hazards. Some places have solid frameworks and policies thanks to technology and community involvement. DRRM is less effective in areas with insufficient money, infrastructure, and public education.

	Mean	Description
Disaster Prevention and Mitigation	3.28	Highly Implemented
Disaster Preparedness	3.36	Highly Implemented
Disaster Response	3.20	Moderately Implemented
Disaster Recovery and Rehabilitation	3.33	Highly Implemented
Extent Implementation of DRRM	3.29	Highly Implemented

Table 1 shows the extent of implementation of the four (4) themes of DRRM by the three (3) clustered schools that are highly implemented, with a mean score of 3.29; this shows that the public secondary schools in Benguet have proactive plans and activities to alleviate these threats toward the learners and the employees. It also implied that the institutions are doing their best to assure the public schools that they will actively implement DRRM in their respective schools. To emphasize the implementation of DRRM in schools, the Department of Education Regional Office requires the regional division offices to submit DRRM reports for project implementation review and review of the DRR policies and standards. The first two themes, disaster preparedness, disaster prevention and mitigation, and Disaster recovery and rehabilitation have the highest mean scores of 3.36, 3.28, and 3.33, respectively, interpreted as highly implemented. This means that this institution is putting more effort into controlling, minimizing, and preparing when calamities strike.

3.2 Extent of Implementation on Disaster Prevention and Mitigation

Disaster prevention and mitigation emphasizes a strong domain to reduce or eliminate the impact of disaster. This implementation varies greatly depending on regional vulnerabilities, governance frameworks, and resource availability.

	Mean	Description
Retrofitting of Infrastructures	2.83	Moderately Implemented
Approved localize policies on Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Implementation	3.22	Moderately Implemented
Implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in line with Climate change Adaptation and Mitigation	3.50	Highly Implemented
Established Early Warning System	3.56	Highly Implemented
Disaster Prevention and Mitigation	3.28	Highly Implemented

It can be seen from Table 2 that both prevention and mitigation are being put into practice. An early warning system can be established by the institutions, which receives a score of 3.56; the implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management following climate change adaptation and mitigation receives a score of 3.50, which is the second highest score. A similar result in the study of Domingo and Ormilla (2022) is that early warning systems are in place in the institutions. On the other hand, with a score of 3.22 and 2.83, respectively, approved localized policies on disaster risk reduction and management implementation and retrofitting of facilities are moderately implemented. This contrasts with the situation where the policies are not implemented at all.

3.3 Extent of Implementation of Disaster Preparedness

A community equipped for disaster preparedness is resilient, as its members know appropriate actions during crises. Understanding how to respond enhances the likelihood of survival.

The table shows the extent of implementing Disaster Preparedness, which has a score of 3.36, interpreted as highly implemented. Of the 15 activities on disaster preparedness, 10 of which are highly implemented rank from highest to lowest and as follows: Conducts quarterly drills alongside students and Identification of evacuation areas with a score of 3.83, DRRM is incorporated in the school curriculum with a score of 3.78, Revisiting the DRRM plan annually with a score of 3.56, Strengthening of partnership to external stakeholders, Posting visible signages or markings indicating warning signs on buildings, playgrounds, and pathways and Appropriate signages are visible to all faculty, staff, students, and visitors to follow with a mean score of 3.39, School Disaster Risk mapping and upgraded on monthly or annual bases and Formulation of the disaster-controlled group with a mean score of 3.33 and the last activity Purchases of disaster equipment and first aid kits with a mean score of 3.28.

On the other hand, five of these are moderately implemented. Rank for highest to lowest, having backup or duplicate school records, and The school has identified temporary learning space and alternative mode of delivering education with a mean score of 3.17; trainings and seminars conducted to increase the level of awareness with a mean score of 3.06, Testing the plans or table tap exercises after crafting with a mean score of 3.00, and the lastly School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management quarterly meeting with a mean score of 2.83.

Table 3: Extent Implementation of Disaster Preparedness

Questions	Mean	DE
School Disaster Risk mapping and upgraded on a monthly or annual basis	3.33	Highly Implemented
Identification of evacuation area	3.83	Highly Implemented
Formulation of disaster-controlled group	3.33	Highly Implemented
Revisiting the DRRM plan annually	3.56	Highly Implemented
Posting visible signages or markings indicating warning signs on buildings, playgrounds, and pathways	3.39	Highly Implemented
School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management quarterly meeting	2.83	Moderately Implemented
Training and seminars conducted to increase the level of awareness	3.06	Moderately Implemented
Strengthening of partnerships with external stakeholders	3.39	Highly Implemented
Testing the plans or table tap exercises after crafting	3.00	Moderately Implemented
Conducts quarterly drills alongside students	3.83	Highly Implemented
DRRM is incorporated into the school curriculum	3.78	Highly Implemented
Purchases of disaster equipment and first aid kits	3.28	Highly Implemented

Having backup or duplicate school records	3.17	Moderately Implemented
Appropriate signage are visible to all faculty, staff, students, and visitors to follow	3.39	Highly Implemented
The school has identified temporary learning space and alternative modes of delivering education	3.17	Moderately Implemented
Disaster Preparedness	3.36	Highly Implemented

3.4 Extent of Implementation of Disaster Response

A disaster response effort is a quick set of actions taken after a disaster to lessen its effects on people, their property, and their ability to provide for their fundamental needs. The level of disaster response strategy varies by region and is influenced by things like infrastructure, government, and how ready the community is, among other things. For disaster response to work well, many groups must work together. These groups should include government agencies, local communities, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs).

Table 4 shows that the extent of implementation of disaster response has a mean score of 3.20, interpreted as moderately implemented. The three activities identified are systematic coordination with parents or guardians during a disaster, the composition of rapid damage and the need analysis team, and systematic response mechanisms in a controlled group. All are moderately implemented, with a mean score of 3.28, 3.22, and 3.11, respectively.

Table 4: Extent of Implementation on Disaster Response

Questions	Mean	DE
Composition of Rapid Damage and need analysis team	3.22	Moderately Implemented
Systematic response mechanism on Disaster Controlled Group	3.11	Moderately Implemented
Systematic coordination to parents or guardians during disaster	3.28	Moderately Implemented
Disaster Response	3.20	Moderately Implemented

3.5 Extent of Implementation of Disaster Recovery and Rehabilitation

Disaster recovery and rehabilitation are critical stages in disaster management, addressing the restoration of properties, livelihood, and economy. The degree of implementation in this area fluctuates significantly and is affected by factors including community resilience.

The extent of disaster recovery and rehabilitation implementation is highly implemented, with a mean score of 3.33. With six activities identified, three activities are highly implemented and as follows Bayanihan program committed by the PTA, Repair of Structural Damages, and Conducting Post-disaster Needs Assessed and proper channelling of result with a mean score of 3.78, 3.61, and 3.39, respectively. On the other hand, three activities are moderately implemented. Post-disaster psychological and mental health programs are in place; alternative temporary classrooms are identified, and alternative livelihood programs are in place with a mean score of 3.22, 3.17, and 2.83.

Table 5: Extent of Implementation on Disaster Recovery and Rehabilitation

Questions	Mean	DE
Conducting Post-disaster Needs Assessments and proper channelling of result	3.39	Highly Implemented
Identified alternative temporary classroom	3.17	Moderately Implemented

Post-disaster psychological and mental health programs in place	3.22	Moderately Implemented
Repair of Structural Damages	3.61	Highly Implemented
Bayanihan program committed by the PTA	3.78	Highly Implemented
An alternative livelihood program is in place	2.83	Moderately Implemented
Disaster Recovery and Rehabilitation	3.33	Highly Implemented

3.6 Implementation of DRRM According to the Municipality the Schools are located

Especially in areas prone to natural disasters, it is crucial for educational institutions to implement Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) measures to safeguard both students and staff. The success of DRRM initiatives may vary greatly depending on factors such as the community's involvement, the local resources, the municipality where the schools are situated, and the degree to which the program is adopted.

Table 6: Implementation of DRRM According to the Municipality the Schools are located

Implementation of DRRM	Municipality	Mean	DE	Kruskal-Wallis Statistic	p-value	Pairwise
Disaster Prevention and Mitigation	Buguias	3.13	MI	3.404ns	0.182	-
	Bokod	3.00	MI			
	La Trinidad	3.53	HI			
Disaster Preparedness	Buguias	3.33	HI	0.093ns	0.955	-
	Bokod	3.35	HI			
	La Trinidad	3.38	HI			
Disaster Response	Buguias	3.17	MI	2.123ns	0.346	-
	Bokod	2.92	MI			
	La Trinidad	3.37	HI			
Disaster Recovery and Rehabilitation	Buguias	3.25	MI	1.726ns	0.422	-
	Bokod	3.17	MI			
	La Trinidad	3.48	HI			
Implementation of DRRM	Buguias	3.22	MI	2.010ns	0.366	-
	Bokod	3.11	MI			
	La Trinidad	3.44	HI			

Overall, schools located in Buguias score between 2.13 and 3.33 across four thematic areas of DRRM, indicating moderate to high implementation. Meanwhile, in Bokod, scores range from 2.92 to 3.35, suggesting a range from mild to high implementation. On the other hand, for schools in La Trinidad, Scores range from 3.37 to 3.53, indicating a higher implementation level than the different municipalities.

P-values of Disaster Prevention and Mitigation, Preparedness, Response, and Recovery and Rehabilitation with p-values of 0.182, 0.955, 0.346, and 0.422, respectively, are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). It suggests that the four thematic areas have no substantial differences in all municipalities. The result indicates that schools in La Trinidad have stronger implementation than those in Buguias and Bokod. On the other hand, there is no strong support suggesting that the statistic is substantial enough to prove that there is a significant difference in the implementation of DRRM

3.7 Training and Seminars needed to be conducted

The ability to prevent, mitigate, and recover from disasters depends on people’s and organizations’ capacity, which is a part of disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM). Strengthening communities, making responses more efficient, and encouraging a mindset of readiness that can all be achieved through organized training programs and seminars.

Table 7: Training and Seminars needed to be conducted

Training	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Incident Command System	17	7.20%	1
First Aid Training	17	7.20%	1
Community First Responder	16	6.78%	6
Basic Life Support	17	7.20%	1
Search and Rescue	16	6.78%	6
Logistics Training	16	6.78%	6
Contingency Planning	17	7.20%	1
Climate Change Action Planning	16	6.78%	6
Mental Health and Psychosocial Support	16	6.78%	6
Livelihood Training	13	5.51%	14
Community-based Disaster Risk Reduction and Management	15	6.36%	12
Public Service Continuity Plan	13	5.51%	14
Rapid Damage and Needs Analysis	17	7.20%	1
Post Disaster and Needs Analysis	16	6.78%	6
Climate and Disaster Risk Assessment (CDRA)	14	5.93%	13

Table 7 shows that out of the 15 activities enumerated, 5 activities are more prioritized disaster management to increase their capabilities by the schools with 7.20%, which are First Aid Training, Basic

Life Support, Incident Command System, Contingency Planning, and Rapid Damage and Needs Analysis are the most frequent activities. While Livelihood Training, Public Service Continuity Plan, and Climate and Disaster Risk Assessment are activities that the schools seem not to prioritize, this does not indicate that they are not a crucial part of disaster management. To conclude, the data suggests that basic life-saving skills, coordination, and rapid assessment are consistently given priority, along with emergency response and preparation. Climate issues and mental health assistance are also receiving attention, but other areas like livelihood training and public service continuity planning are not as much given attention.

3.8 Encountered in implementing the four thematic areas of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management are discussed.

The ability to prevent, mitigate, and recover from disasters depends on people and organizations having the capacity to be a part of disaster risk reduction and management (DRRM). Conducting skill enhancement increases community resilience, strengthens response productivity, and promotes a proactive environment.

The primary challenges that the schools are encountering are insufficient budgets, which are the most challenging, and the next are the additional responsibilities of DRRM coordinators and the heavy workload of these coordinators. The lack of teacher training in DRRM and weak coordination with disaster management agencies. On the other hand, a strong and positive that can impact the result of their implementation is the strong support by The Local Government Unit of the SDRRM, the parent's support of the implementation of SDRRM, and The division office's full support with the SDRRM to provide training equipment and policy.

Table 8: Encountered in implementing the four thematic areas of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management are discussed.

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
The school DRRM coordinator is well-trained	6	5.17%	8
Being a school DRRM coordinator is an additional function	16	13.79%	2
The Local Government Unit has a full support on the SDRRM	14	12.07%	6
The division office has a full support with the SDRRM to provide trainings equipment and policy	16	13.79%	2
The parents support the implementation of SDRRM	15	12.93%	4
The DRRM coordinator has a lot of tasks to do in addition to his/her regular load	15	12.93%	4
Not enough budget for the implementation of disaster risk reduction and management	17	14.66%	1
The faculty are not supportive on the programs	4	3.45%	10
The teacher does not have trainings in disaster risk reduction and management	7	6.03%	7
Weak coordination between schools and disaster management agency such as BDRRMC and MDRRMO	6	5.17%	8

4. Discussion

The implementation of the four themes of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management is to ensure the safety of every individual in the community. It envisions having a community that is Disaster resilient, stronger, and proactive in governance as it aims to shift from being reactive to a proactive community. The 2011–2028 NDRRM Framework contemplates having “safer, adaptive, and disaster-resilient Filipino communities toward sustainable development.” With this vision, it is proper to check on implementing the four themes in the education sector, as it has a community where they belong to the vulnerable group. The prevention and mitigation show high implementation and compliance with DepEd Order No. 33 Series of 2021. It is worth noting that, compared with the study of Comighud (2020), the Benguet division shows a slight difference in terms of disaster Prevention and Mitigation. This difference underscores the importance of continuous improvement and adaptation in these measures. Furthermore, Baluran's (2023) research confirms that public schools in Cotabato demonstrate high disaster preparedness implementation. It indicates that most public schools in the Philippines strive to enhance their resilience to mitigate or avert the effects of disasters. Domingo and Ormilla (2022) found that one of the best practices observed was disseminating information on emergency protocols. Early warning systems are identified as one of the most in place in all schools as this is very important to track hazards so proactive measures can be considered. This knowledge was uncovered through their research.

The outcome indicates deficiencies within the system that necessitate attention during the execution of disaster response measures. It also suggests that training or retraining in particular skills needs to be organized. As shown in Table 4, basic life support and first aid training are some of the

skills required during response. It underscores the fact that not all personnel in the institutions are well-trained or have the corresponding skills related to DCG. In the study of Balanggoy, H. K. (2024), the capacity in terms of skills of the public secondary schools is not well established. Similar results were found in the study by Rico (2019), which found that educators have inadequate knowledge and skill in basic life support and search and rescue. With this, the respondents believe that training is the key to becoming more knowledgeable and skilled in areas that need improvement. According to Harward (2017), the best way to improve performance is to be trained and practice the desired skills. Still, the problem is that it is expensive, which goes back to the agency's fund, which is insufficient to support all the programs and activities of the schools. With this, improving the specific activity in all thematic areas will benefit the school and the community more.

Moreover, it is worth noting that the implementation of disaster preparedness is significantly higher in these clusters. In contrast, the La Trinidad cluster effectively incorporates all four thematic areas. Some possibilities can contribute to and affect the findings. First, as claimed by the respondents, budget allocation is one of the major challenges for schools in implementing programs related to DRRM, as reflected in Table 8. Secondly, according to Col (2007), as cited by Domingo et al. (2018), The local government plays a crucial role before, during, and after disasters. This role provides reassurance and confidence, as the LGU has direct authority over its constituents and is expected to understand their requirements. As mandated by the Local Government Code of 1991, the local government unit will supervise disaster risk reduction and management. The LGU must have the authority to act independently and make proactive decisions based on the circumstances of its constituents, with the backing of higher levels of government.

Furthermore, the potential risks are alarming because once a hazard strikes an area, like an earthquake or typhoon, it can easily collapse or be destroyed. According to the report of Nicholls (2022), the secretary of education announced that the Department's annual budget has little funding for infrastructure.

With this, the parents are actively helping restore the school after it was devastated because, in return, it will also help protect their children from getting injured or being harmed. The success of the Bayanihan program underscores the importance of community involvement in disaster recovery efforts, a fact that we should all appreciate and support. According to the study by Pfefferbaum et al. (2010), parents play an important role in protecting their children from possible exposure that can harm or cause accidents after a disaster. However, the research conducted by Escobar (2021) presents a contrasting perspective to the research findings. Escobar's study challenges the notion that the absence of support from learners' parents in implementing DRRM programs and activities is one of the top five challenges teachers face in Marikina City. Cultural differences may influence these factors that affect an individual's social responsibilities.

Furthermore, the problems the schools encountered were also confirmed by [Escobar](#) (2021) in Marikina, which needed clarification on the funding source and the unavailability of funds to implement activities related to DRRM, confirmed the result. It only implies that it's not just the Benguet division that experiences budget shortages to implement DRRM; it's the problem of the entire DepEd system. The study of Arierto, C. et al. (2023) shows that one of the school's common problems is a need for more budget.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

With the limited funding in the education system, schools are still striving to create a safe and resilient community for learners. The personnel of the schools are doing their best to be more proactive in ensuring the implementation of DRRM. With the challenges encountered in disaster risk reduction and management, safety is still one of their priorities.

These recommendations, drawn from the study's findings, to significantly enhance our disaster risk reduction and management efforts. We urge you to continuously coordinate with the Municipal and Provincial Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Council, the Office of Civil Defense CAR, and other government agencies. By doing so, you can be one of the beneficiaries of their

capacity-building programs and provide technical assistance in formulating plans and implementing projects. I encourage you to explore collaborative alliances with private entities to secure financial support for training initiatives, projects, and various undertakings. Implementing an annual or biannual skills refresher course for teachers would involve the participation of the school nurse and physician. Partner with any nursing school to provide community services and disaster nursing to teach skills in basic life support, first aid training, and other health-related topics to the teachers and learners.

Funding: This research was funded by Benguet State University

Acknowledgements: To all participants and the funding agency thank you.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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